

AMIR TEMUR'S CONTRIBUTION TO SCIENCE.**Melikuzieva Movluda**

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ANNOTATSIYA: The article discusses Amir Temur's contribution to science and education, as well as Amir Temur's fair rule in his work, as well as his thoughts and principles in state management.

Key words: Timur's laws, education, upbringing, principle, teachings.

Amir Temur brought craftsmen from other countries to Movorounnahr. Madrasahs, observatories, libraries were built in Samarkand and Herat. Wonderful works on medicine, geography, history, literature, mathematics, astronomy, philosophy, natural science were created. During the lifetime of Amir Temur, a special work dedicated to his military art and the style of state management was created, which became famous under the name "Temur Tuzuklari". This work is considered to have been written down from Temur's own words. In it, who is to be relied upon in the management of the state, the position (direction) and duties of the holders of the throne, (election of ministers and army chiefs, salaries of soldiers), the procedure for managing the country, the appearance of emirs, ministers and other officials in front of the throne the procedure for awarding the special services rendered and the duties and tasks of statesmen and army chiefs are described in respect of others. Amir Temur followed the following twelve principles throughout his life:

- He supported the religion of Islam everywhere and at all times.
- He managed state affairs on the basis of a council.
- The Sultanate conducted its affairs through compromise.
- Managed state affairs based on laws and regulations.
- Showed respect to emirs and soldiers.
- He relied on justice and honesty.
- He showed respect to the citizens.
- Azmu worked hard.
- Raiyat was constantly aware of the situation.
- Turku showed respect to different categories of Tajik and Arab students.
- He did not forget his friends and helped them.
- He respected the soldiers everywhere.

Amir Temur built his empire and raised its economic and cultural power to the highest level. In conclusion, the period from the second half of the XIVth century to the XVII th century was a period of economic, social, and spiritual growth in

Movarounnahr. Amir Temur, the founder of the centralized state, managed to turn Movarunnahr into the most powerful state in Europe and the East. Amir Temur, the owner of the Great Sultanate, who had such titles as Koragon - son-in-law of the Khan, Qutbiddin - leader of the times, Abulmansur - conqueror, winner, master - star, born in lucky signs, Amir Temur is strict with the motto "Strength is in justice". acted and ruled the state. The pattern of Amir Temur's seal means "Rosti-rusti" ("You will be saved if you are right") or "You will be saved if you are honest". Mirzo Ulug'bek lived and created in Movarounnahr, in the period of cultural development and interest in worldly sciences throughout Central Asia. He is one of the great figures who brought the science and culture of the peoples of Central Asia to the world level.

1. Fertilizers in "Temur tuzuklari" can be divided into the following groups according to their nature and function:
2. 1. About religion and sharia.
3. 2. Regarding the state and its administration.
4. 3. Regarding holding a council.
5. 4. Regarding the king and ministers.
6. 1 Justice and injustice.
7. 2. Unity of word and trust.
8. 3. Friendship and enmity.
9. 4. Bravery and cowardice.
10. Words and sweet talk.

Examples of wisdom from "Timur tuziklari":

11. Justice wins, not enmity.
12. Let the speaker live as a fool, and let the listener die as a wise man.
13. He who did not have a father does not know the value of a father.
14. Do not be afraid of the enemy, be afraid of the hypocrite.
15. Faith. But doubt it.
16. Strength is in justice.
17. Friendship is tested.
18. Be the head of an ant before the tail of an elephant.
19. A horse rides a horse.
20. The brave is known in battle, the wise in counsel.
21. There is no strength without unity.

In conclusion, Amir Temur was a great leader, a righteous man, and his work in the field of education and science development left a deep mark on the pages of history.

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